

LEARNERS' INTERESTS, ATTITUDES AND COMPLIANCE TO MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING DURING PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

Suspended Face-to-face learning engagement of students and teachers has transitioned to adopting the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE – LCP), where most schools implemented the Modular Distance Learning modality where learners undergo a self-guided learning approach. Thus, this study investigates the learners' interests, attitudes, and compliance to modular distance learning of 100 Senior High students who took the modular distance learning. Deductive thematic analysis and survey were employed as a research instrument. They were asked to answer an original survey questionnaire to assess their study habits to extract responses on the interest, attitudes, and compliance of learners with the learning modules. The research findings showed that understandability, difficulty, and presentation of the lessons of the modules keep the respondent interested. The parental support and environmental setting of the learners enable them to maintain a positive mindset throughout the process. The learners were compliant in accomplishing their requirements with less supervision and to the point of neglecting sleep when certain tasks require immediate completion. Results dictated that students have to adjust to a whole new way of learning, instead of complaining students always did their best to accomplish their task. Each student is an individual with his/her special aptitude and interest, intending to help each student to think for himself, and allow individuality to each learner. This informs the parents of the undertakings of their children and can provide support, encouragement, and availability of resources. The government can support the students by intensifying and making existing programs available virtually and tapped the different agencies for collaborative events in enriching the current modality. This study is important to serve as a springboard for future improvement of the schools' existing programs and guidelines on implementing modular distance learning.

Keywords: Interests, Attitudes, Compliance, Modular Distance Learning, Learners, COVID-19 Pandemic